

A new European project empowers local communities and beyond with efficient waste-to-hydrogen solutions

The CARMA-H2 project, supported by funding from the Clean Hydrogen Partnership, aims to promote efficient hydrogen production from waste. The aim is to ensure strong energy performance with a fully carbon-negative approach.

The role of biogas in reducing CO₂ emissions in the EU by 2050 is crucial, especially as demand from industry and the energy sector is expected to rise significantly. Therefore, prioritising biogas production through waste-to-hydrogen conversion is essential. Using waste as a feedstock for hydrogen production not only minimises CO₂ emissions compared to direct biogas combustion but also fosters a circular economy.

In this context, the CARMA-H2 project aims to harness innovative technology for the direct delivery of purified and pressurized hydrogen while simultaneously generating food-grade CO₂ through a liquefaction process. By recycling off-gas produced during liquefaction, CARMA-H2 enhances overall efficiency and supports the broader goals of sustainable energy production.

Additionally, CARMA-H2 tackles the inefficiencies and economic challenges of traditional hydrogen production methods that are unsuitable for smaller biogas facilities. By introducing an integrated novel

modular reactor, the project streamlines the conventional six-step waste-to-hydrogen conversion process into a single operation, efficiently converting waste into hydrogen to meet the pressing energy needs of small to medium-sized communities.

Reflecting on the potential of the integrated novel modular reactor, Nancy Tarjenian Astour, the project coordinator and Technology Business Development Manager at the Asociación de la Industria Navarra (AIN), shares: “The project provides us with a unique opportunity to explore the technical feasibility of this innovative technology and showcase its potential to transform waste into hydrogen efficiently and sustainably, simplifying the entire process for smaller-scale applications”.

The project was launched in October 2024, with Mikel Irujo Amezaga, Minister of Economic and Business Development of Navarre, participating in the inaugural meeting. During his speech, he highlighted the importance of CARMA-H2 for promoting environmental sustainability and meeting local energy needs.

Coordinated by AIN, the project unites 11 partners who will collaborate over the next 48 months to advance hydrogen production and CO₂ recovery technologies. Together, they aim to empower local communities and foster a resilient, climate-conscious energy future across Europe and beyond.

Co-funded by the European Union. The project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Clean Hydrogen Joint Undertaking. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Contacts

Project coordinator:

Nancy Tarjenian Astour, Asociación de la Industria Navarra (AIN), NTarjenian@ain.es

Communication Managers:

Ani Asatryan, Project Management Officer, ICONS, ani.asatryan@icons.it

Davide Valenti, Communication Officer, ICONS, davide.valenti@icons.it

